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D5.4 – Blue-Cloud VRE Common Services 2nd release

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
CMS	Content Management System
CVS	Code Versioning System
DD&AS	Data Discovery & Access Service
DNS	Domain Name System
D4Science	Data Infrastructure promoting Open Science (managed by CNR)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOVs	Essential Ocean Variables
GRSF	Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries
GUI	Graphical User Interface
JSON	Javascript Object Notation
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OIDC	OpenID Connect
RIA	Rich Internet Application
UI	User Interface
UMA	User-Managed Access
VLab	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

Keywords

EOSC; Virtual Labs; Big Data; Virtual Research Environment; e-infrastructures

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable documents the design principles and software architecture characterising the release and development of the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) common services, namely the analytics computing framework, the catalogue framework, the storage framework and the enabling framework components. This report is the second of two versions, each one describing the design associated with a specific version of the VRE. This deliverable D5.4 provides the updated and extended version of D5.1 “Blue-Cloud VRE Common Services 1st Release” [8]. The document presents the current state of the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) common services, detailing both the new components introduced in the period M13 to M36 and the enhancements applied to the existing ones to ensure compliance with interoperability, scalability, and robustness requirements. Overall, deliverable D5.4 provides a consolidated, fully up-to-date view of the Blue-Cloud VRE common services architecture, covering functional capabilities, API exposure, deployment configuration, and integration status as of the end of the second reporting period.

The deliverable consists of six sections.

- Section 1 briefly introduces the role of this deliverable in the development and delivery of the Blue-Cloud VRE common services.
- Section 2 describes the Blue-Cloud VRE logical architecture of the common services and how they relate to the other services available in the VRE.
- Section 3, 4, 5 and 6 document the release of the Blue-Cloud VRE common services available at M36, reporting the design principles and reference software architecture of the released solutions. Specifically, Section 3 describes the analytics computing framework which includes the Analytics Engine, Galaxy workflows, the RStudio and the Jupyter Notebooks via JupyterHub. Section 4 presents the VRE Catalogue framework and its components, and section 5 reports on the Storage framework.
- Finally, section 6 concludes the report by illustrating the services composing the Enabling framework, which is used as a common ground for all the above-mentioned frameworks.

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1. Introduction

The Horizon Europe Blue-Cloud initiative started its journey in 2019 with the aim to create a European Open Science Cloud for marine data by federating data and e-infrastructures and making data products and technologies available as open science resources for the broad marine research community. Since 2023, the Blue-Cloud 2026 follow-up project aims at a further evolution of this pilot ecosystem into a Federated European Ecosystem to deliver FAIR & Open data and analytical services, instrumental for deepening research of oceans, EU seas, coastal & inland waters. Building upon the pilot Blue-Cloud project, the current Blue-Cloud technical framework is extensible and open by design, constantly evolving according to the needs of the community, facilitating collaborative research and the uptake of Open Science principles, through a distinguished set of services. Among those, the following are considered Blue-Cloud core services:

- The [Data Discovery and Access Service](#) (DD&AS) is an overarching service to facilitate federated queries and retrieval, and smart sharing of multi-disciplinary datasets with human and machine users.
- The Blue-Cloud [Virtual Research Environment \(VRE\)](#) orchestrates the computing and analytical services in specific integrated and managed applications exploiting federated Blue-Cloud data resources as well as external data resources.
- Five [dedicated Virtual Laboratories](#) (VLabs) co-created with top-level marine researchers to showcase the power of the Blue-Cloud Open Science platform via real life scientific cases [5].

This Deliverable **D5.4 “Blue-Cloud VRE Common Services 2nd release”** provides the updated and extended version of **D5.1 “Blue-Cloud VRE Common Services 1st Release”** [8]. The document presents the current state of the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) common services, detailing both the new components introduced in the period up to M36 and the enhancements applied to the existing ones to ensure compliance with interoperability, scalability, and robustness requirements. Overall, D5.4 provides a consolidated, fully up-to-date view of the Blue-Cloud VRE common services architecture, covering functional capabilities, API exposure, deployment configuration, and integration status as of the end of the second reporting period.

These VRE services rely on the D4Science infrastructure [2, 4] and utilise the gCube open-source technology [1]. D4Science provides the resilient, scalable and policy-compliant foundation on which the VRE services operate, ensuring reliability, high availability and sustained performance. The adoption of gCube open-source components also guarantees flexibility and extensibility, enabling the continuous evolution of services through modular updates and interoperability enhancements.

All VRE services are deployed within the Blue-Cloud VRE Gateway, which is accessible to authenticated users at <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org>. The Gateway acts as the central access point to the services and Virtual Labs, offering researchers a unified and coherent entry to the Blue-Cloud environment.

2. VRE logical architecture and common services

Figure 1 illustrates the Blue-Cloud VRE Common Services logical architecture, which supports the creation of Blue-Cloud Virtual Laboratories. The VRE is built by exploiting the Virtual Machines operated and provisioned by D4Science, together with services for their management and administration (VRE federated resources). Above this layer, several services form the enabling framework, which is essential for supporting the operation of all services and VREs. Specifically, this framework includes:

1. **Information System service:** This service allows for the dynamic (de)registration and discovery of all VRE resources (data sources, services, computational nodes, etc.), by users and other services;
2. **Identity and Access Management (IAM) service:** Responsible for handling authentication and authorisation services, as well as auditing services. It is capable of granting and tracking access and usage actions from users; and
3. **VRE Management System service:** This service facilitates the deployment of specialised V Labs based on a selected subset of applications.

Figure 1 The Blue-Cloud VRE common services logical architecture

On top of this layer, three frameworks, namely the Storage Framework, the Catalogue Framework and the Analytics Computing Framework are built to provide common facilities to users.

The **Analytics Computing Framework**, to date, offers set of data analytical services that can be requested and customised in the V Labs:

- **Analytics engine:** This service features the following two engines.

- **DataMiner:** the engine that was used in Blue-Cloud and will be maintained in Blue-Cloud 2026. It comprises a rich array of ready to use analytical methods ranging from data clustering methods to geospatial data analytics, occurrence data management, and species distribution maps generation.
- **Cloud Computing Platform (CCP):** a more recent processing engine that follows the same design principles and core features as DataMiner. Within Blue Cloud 2026 CCP is being further developed in order to extend its capabilities by incorporating current advancements in information technology and software engineering.
- **RStudio:** This service allows users to perform online statistical analyses. It offers a predefined list of R packages, and each VLab can define its RStudio server configurations. The configurations include a Standard (4 cores/8GB RAM) and a Large (8 cores/32GB RAM) one.
- **JupyterLab:** a web-based interactive development environment designed for Jupyter notebooks, code, and data. It allows users to configure and arrange the user interface to support a wide range of workflows in data science, scientific computing, and machine learning.
- **ShinyProxy:** a reliable platform for deploying Shiny applications in enterprise contexts without restrictions on concurrent usage. Shiny is an R package that enables the creation of interactive web applications, and a possibility to use a Python version has recently been introduced.
- **Galaxy:** scientific workflow platform designed to make computational workflows accessible to researchers who do not have experience in programming or systems administration. Although originally developed to support genomics research, it has since evolved into a domain independent workflow management system that is widely used across many scientific disciplines.

The **Catalogue Framework** primary component is the VRE Data Catalogue. This service is built on open-source technology for data catalogues, CKAN (ckan.org). Through this Catalogue users can search and browse data, products, and resources (posters, deliverables, etc) of interest from the Blue-Cloud community.

The **Storage Framework** operates transparently to users and virtualises the available storage technologies and their actual physical hardware.

3. Analytics Computing Framework

The Analytics Computing Framework includes a suite of services and components designed to support data processing, analytical computation and data mining on heterogeneous information sets. **Section 3.1** describes the two engines available for the import and execution of analytical methods: the **Cloud Computing Platform (CCP)**, which is the more recent engine that has evolved during the reporting period, and **DataMiner**, the engine used in the previous Blue Cloud project, which continued to be maintained but not further developed.

Section 3.2 covers several interactive and workflow-oriented analytical environments. It primarily focuses on **JupyterHub**, which enables the use of the **RStudio** application for online statistical analysis and the JupyterLab application, a web-based, interactive development environment for Jupyter notebooks.

Section 3.3 describes the support offered by the VRE for deploying ShinyApps through **ShinyProxy**, as well as other container-based applications for interactive visualisation and custom analytical tools. The section also covers **Container Orchestration**, which is a key component of the Blue Cloud VRE. Two technologies are used: **Docker Swarm**, which manages Docker containers across a cluster of virtual machines using a manager and agent model with a least-utilised allocation strategy, and **Kubernetes**, which provides advanced capabilities for the automated deployment, scaling, and operation of containers across host clusters.

Section 3.4 presents the support for **Galaxy Workflows**. Galaxy¹ is a free and open-source platform for data analysis, workflow authoring, training and education, tool publishing, and infrastructure management. Within Blue Cloud 2026, the integration of Galaxy enables users to execute complex multi-step analyses through reproducible workflows and to interoperate with CCP, strengthening the capacity of the framework for open and transparent computational science.

3.1. Analytics Engines

3.1.1. Cloud Computing Platform

Over the past decade, the Information and Communication Technology domain has undergone significant evolution, marked by the widespread adoption of microservice-based development approaches. These approaches have enabled substantial improvements in interoperability and composability, even when software components operate within distributed environments.

REST APIs have become the predominant mechanism for implementing web services, while web components and micro-frontends extend service-oriented principles to graphical user interfaces. At the same time, the emergence of new programming languages with reduced footprint, increased domain

¹ <https://galaxyproject.org>

specificity, and simplified syntax has been facilitated by the greater architectural flexibility introduced by these trends.

As a result, the adoption of microservice and cloud-native approaches has led to the emergence of new requirements and novel patterns have emerged at the operational level as well. The so-called concept of “containerisation”, serving as the lightweight alternative to virtualisation of computing resources, has become the de facto standard for packaging and provisioning software. Tools and languages have been created for the automation of provisioning, microservice orchestration, inspection and monitoring of software and infrastructure components.

CCP Design principles and implementation

The vast landscape of new opportunities described above, in addition to the greatly increased requirements and expectations, represented the major drivers for the design and development of the CCP. This platform represents the result of a comprehensive re-evaluation of the existing DataMiner solution. After a critical overview of the current solution, DataMiner and its Software Importer (SAI) (cf. Section 3.1.2), a use case-driven analysis of the requirements for CCP has been performed.

The following use cases have been identified:

- **Use case 0 - Workspace abstractions:** CCP should be able to access file resources stored on different distributed workspace abstractions.
- **Use case 1 - Access Data as a Service:** CCP should be able to access data exposed as services.
- **Use case 2 - Low-level polyglot:** CCP should natively support as many programming and scripting languages as possible.
- **Use case 3 - High-level polyglot:** CCP should support different execution environments for scripts and applications.
- **Use case 4 - Support complex tools:** CCP should support complex tools that could have been used in pre-existing workflows.
- **Use case 5 - Support coarse grained parallelism:** CCP should support the possibility of subdividing scripts into parallel tasks.
- **Use case 6 - Support fine grained parallelism:** CCP should support the exploitation of parallel execution environments.
- **Use case 7 - Link to structured code repositories:** CCP should enable access to code stored on different code and artefact repositories.
- **Use case 8 - Develop with non-headless workflows:** CCP should support environments with their own visual or interactive frontend.
- **Use case 9 - Discovery, consolidation and community driven growth:** It should be possible to discover consolidated data sources, methods and algorithms, both interactively and programmatically.

CCP is a sophisticated system of distributed components encompassing different technological and operational domains. This system includes a plethora of resources (hardware, virtual machines, databases and datastores) and processes such as orchestration logic, application and integration software developed

on purpose or made available by the open-source community. At the bottom of these stacks lie the physical resources which can be anything from full-blown datacentres to personal laptops. Each physical host can provide its own set of **services** including storage facilities, code repositories, databases and more. A special physical host is represented by the D4Science platform where the CCP core runs together with other core essential services. Most importantly, a physical host can provide a **computing infrastructure** which represents the set of computing resources used to run **methods** in **executions** performed on compatible **runtimes**.

A method is a lightweight data structure that describes an algorithm, procedure or function. This descriptor provides information about input parameters, expected output results, authorship and versioning. Most importantly, it defines the compatibility with one runtime and the affinity to one or more computing infrastructures. Method descriptors are all kept inside a dedicated **method repository** hosted by the D4Science data centre.

In order to be executable, a method has to be associated with a runtime, which can be seen as a (Docker) container. This container is able to provide everything needed by the method including its operating system and application dependencies. Runtimes are complex and “large” artefacts that are kept in specialised **runtime repositories**. One such repository is hosted by the D4Science data centre, but others can be provided among the services of a data centre. Additionally, access to public runtime repositories offered by third parties is also feasible.

The **execution** of a method is a complex process that involves the following macro phases:

- delivering a method descriptor and a compatible runtime to one of the affine infrastructures;
- bootstrapping the runtime and deploying the method;
- running the method by conveying the user provided inputs;
- monitoring the execution by forwarding real-time logs to the requesting user;
- uploading the generated; and
- cleaning up by destroying the dedicated runtime.

All the information recorded during the execution of a method is stored in a dedicated **execution repository**. The execution repository serves as a temporary storage that helps users track their executions. Upon completion, an execution can be archived, restored or resubmitted.

These operations are coordinated by an internal piping and wiring network. In order to participate as a computing infrastructure, a data centre has to provide a **controller** component that represents the infrastructure side termination of the wiring and piping. Users can interact with the CCP and its features in a way that hides away most of this complexity. This can be done either programmatically or by accessing simple widgets embedded in web pages or portals or more complex applications. This architectural vision translates to the logical architecture depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Logical architecture design

The logical architecture in Figure 2 illustrates the natively distributed nature of CCP. Starting from the top, **infrastructures** are computing resources that will run CCP executions (shown as green Es). These infrastructures can be hosted in datacentres. The term data centre actually encompasses everything ranging from simple laptops up to clusters of **nodes**. *Nodes* refer to machines, such as servers or PCs, delegated to run the actual execution of methods.

A computing infrastructure can be connected to the CCP core by a **Controller** component. Controllers are processes that communicate via a dedicated API with the CCP in order to poll for *tasks* to perform on the **Infrastructure** they control. Tasks may include deploying new runtimes, provisioning and execution of methods, and reporting on the overall status of the Infrastructure. In order to keep the current state for CCP, a repository of methods and executions is implemented. For methods, the descriptor data structures are kept in the proper repository.

For each execution, the repository stores a lot of information that allows for an exact reproduction of the execution:

- the method descriptor;

- the descriptor of the infrastructure that executed the method;
- the execution request with all input parameters;
- the standard output and error channels;
- all the data that is produced and uploaded by the method; and
- metadata identifying the user that requested the execution.

A repository for runtimes is provided in order to provide trusted and validated runtimes, with the flexibility to utilise external repositories or those provided by the datacentre hosting infrastructures. All the components adhere to well-defined and where possible, standard-compliant REST APIs. This allows users to programmatically interact with CCP without having to know the complex architecture.

A set of widgets (as shown in Figure 4), such as “Method List”, “Method Form”, “Execution Form”, and “Execution Monitor”, is delivered in the form of *web components*. These components can be embedded into web pages, portals or other web-based complex applications such as JupyterHub. Two core applications are provided in D4Science portals involved in Blue-Cloud by combining the available widgets: the “CCP Method Manager and Importer” and “CCP Method Execution Manager”. Given that many of the operations involved are lengthy and asynchronous, CCP includes a *Logging Service* that is used to send back real-time notifications to user components about the state of a particular process. These notifications include advancement of Executions, advertisement of Infrastructures status updates, and error conditions.

All complex processes involved in CCP are implemented as workflows inside a *Workflow Orchestrator*. This Orchestrator not only provides a high level of flexibility and customisation, but also allows for a centralised endpoint to monitor progress and check for errors that may occur. At the foundation of all interactions among external actors, such as users and Controllers, a strong authentication and authorisation mechanism is enforced by *Identity and Access Management* (cf. Section 6.1). This mechanism not only enables security requirements, rather it also implements ownership attribution and auditing.

Figure 3 depicts a detailed technical view of the CCP instance that is currently available in the Blue-Cloud VRE.

Figure 3 Detailed CCP architecture in Blue-Cloud VRE

CCP is packaged as a Docker stack that is deployed in the D4Science data centre at the CNR premises in Pisa. Access to the internal components, either through APIs or Widgets, is controlled by a Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) that authenticates and authorises every operation. Security enforcement is achieved in cooperation with the D4Science Identity and Access Management (IAM) service, which is built on Keycloak (cf. Section 6.1).

Harbor is used to implement the runtime repository, or container registry. Currently Docker is supported in production as the type of runtime. Controllers are deployed outside the CCP stack “in front of” the Computing infrastructure they control. Communication towards CCP is performed via authenticated HTTP calls, in order to grant access from any point of the Web. In the current deployment, there are two infrastructures available: one in a data centre in Pisa (CNR), and the second in Catania (GARR-CT). Two main applications have been provided for Blue-Cloud users (Method importer and Method runner) as a combination of the developed UI Components.

Figure 4 shows the Web User Interfaces of the CCP available in the Blue-Cloud VRE. Specifically:

- Method List example: to list of the available methods. Searchable by name, description and keywords. Item is draggable to an Execution Form;
- A Method Form example: to specify a Method according to the OGC Process specification data model. Provide authorship and version information, naming, keywords, inputs, outputs and provisioning information;
- Execution Form example: to request the execution of a method by providing inputs. Allow for code generation in order to request an execution programmatically in languages such as Python, JPython for Jupyter, R, Julia; and
- Execution Monitor example: for the execution tracking with real time streaming of standard output and error logs produced by the method execution. Extra functionality like execution archiving, restoring or replay, code generation for programmatic resubmission of executions in common languages such as Python, JPython for Jupyter, R, Julia.

Figure 4 Some examples of CCP UI Components

At the time of writing, many features that are now available in the current version of CCP have been implemented after getting valuable suggestions from the Project WP3 and WP4 members. For instance, the feature of having standard output and error channels of the method execution reflected to the Execution Monitor (See Figure 4 bottom right).

Additionally, during the reporting period (a) the encoding of execution scripts has been made safer, the (b) possibility to use other runtime repositories has been finalised, and (c) the widget realising the method execution form has been improved by introducing the possibility to define a cardinality for input parameters and the possibility to upload small files as input values. Finally, the following enhancements have been added:

- Method lifecycle tracking, in order to keep a history of the important events related to a Method (Creation, sharing, updating);
- Clone functionality for a Method has been enhanced with the “derive facet” which provides the possibility to preserve a link to the cloned source Method;
- New mechanism of notifications to inform Infrastructure Managers of the creation of a new Method and VRE/VLab Managers when a Method is shared in their context.

During the reporting period, significant effort was dedicated to fixing, refining, and improving the CCP across several areas. From an architectural perspective, the integration of the CCP with both Galaxy and AI4EOSC/iMAGINE was investigated, implemented, and successfully proven. Specifically, this makes it possible to execute generic or domain-specific CCP Methods directly from within the Galaxy Workflows environment as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 CCP Integration with Galaxy Workflows

The required configuration resources can be generated through CCP UI widgets and seamlessly installed into Galaxy. In addition, generic CCP Methods capable of invoking Galaxy tools or workflows have been

developed and delivered as proof-of-concept implementations, demonstrating the bidirectional operability between the two systems.

The integration with AI4EOSC/Imagine artefacts was also validated by implementing a sample Method that makes use of one of the algorithms provided by the framework, specifically, the Plant Classification model. This example confirms the feasibility of incorporating AI4EOSC/iMAGINE components into the CCP execution ecosystem.

Figure 6 CCP Integration with AI4EOSC/iMAGINE artefacts

Another architectural improvement is represented by the replacement of the storage for execution outputs. The adoption of an S3-compatible object storage module inside Blue-Cloud VRE allowed switching from the previous storage, which was a slow NFS based solution, to a more robust and performing implementation. After some tuning and fixing of the implementation, CCP is now able to manage method execution outputs without any limit on size or number.

Finally, a significant part of the tasks involved in the complex workflow that controls method execution has been inline, thus moving them from the external workflow controller to an internal one, making them extremely faster and much more stable. The user experience has improved dramatically in terms of feedback when a new execution is requested.

Several improvements have also been implemented on the execution infrastructure side. The Ansible-based implementation of controllers has been migrated from the old, unstable API to Ansible-runner with an immediate improvement in terms of code quality, stability and safety in concurrency management. The polling activity of Docker/Swarm-based controllers has been rewritten from a naive approach to a “Reactive polling strategy,” which allows for significant optimisation in resource usage on both controllers and CCP. The checking of method status on Docker/Swarm-based infrastructures has been completely rewritten by introducing a specific Ansible plugin that atomically checks for the status of containers and takes decisions about the method outcome in cooperation with CCP. This allowed to clean-up a lot of hacky custom code on the controller side and enabled a much better control of the method’s overall

lifecycle. Thanks to this rewriting several tricky issues (especially related to execution termination) could be removed. In addition, the current implementation has opened up the design and implementation of a generic and uniform solution for more fine-grained progress reporting of executions.

From a more functional viewpoint, the most significant addition to CCP is the WPS2 interface. Now, CCP can be invoked programmatically, not only through its original REST/JSON-based interface (OGC Processes 1.2 API), but also through the OGC WPS 2 interface, which supports POST XML, POST SOAP, and GET dialects.

All the maintenance and system administration aspects have been improved and automated. CCP deployment and update is now completely based on Ansible with no more manual interactions needed. The user interface is deployed automatically in every VRE, Vlab or Workbench or context in general. The overall observability of the system has been improved by implementing dedicated metrics exporters, health checks and alerting rules. All of those have been integrated with the Blue-Cloud VRE observability framework based on de facto standards like Prometheus, Grafana and Uptime Kuma, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 CCP integration in the Grafana (above) and Uptime Kuma tools

Additionally, the user interfaces have undergone significant improvements, in addition to the small bug fixes. In particular:

- *Migration to Bootstrap 5.0.2*: all UI code has been cleaned up, modernised, and fully migrated to Bootstrap 5.0.2, improving consistency, responsiveness, and maintainability.
- *Revised Output Widget*: the output viewer has been completely redesigned to provide a smoother browsing experience, especially when handling a large number of outputs.
- *Improved Output Accessibility*: users can now open outputs directly in a separate browser tab, making inspection and comparison more convenient.
- *New Execution Archive Browser*: a dedicated tab has been introduced for browsing executions that have been archived to the Workspace, simplifying access to historical runs.
- *Expanded Code Exporters*: alongside Python, R, and Jupyter Notebooks, new exporters have been added for Bash, Julia, and Galaxy, significantly broadening the range of supported computational environments.
- *New Geographic and Workspace Widgets*: additional widgets have been implemented to support geographic input formats (WKT, GeoJSON, KML) and to enable intuitive browsing of the D4Science Workspace.
- *Enhanced Method Definition Widget*: inputs and outputs can now be reordered, and the scripts editor has been redesigned with an integrated preview of the generated code, improving clarity during method development.

3.1.2. Data Miner

The DataMiner (DM) [7] engine includes a set of services and components for performing data processing and mining on information sets. Analytical methods employed by users can be developed in almost any programming language (R, Java, Python, Fortran, Octave, etc.) and then imported via the Software and Algorithms Importer (SAI) and executed via the DataMiner engine. Once imported through SAI, DataMiner offers these scripts as a Service, handling aspects like multi-tenancy and simultaneous usage. This system also simplifies script updates for scientists, eliminating the need for extensive re-deployment processes. Essentially, SAI facilitates the creation of processes that operate on the Blue-Cloud VRE Cloud computing platform, accessible through the WPS standard.

To import a script, one must follow three steps in SAI:

1. Define the input, output, and types for the primary script that coordinates the process.
2. Construct the Software: This step involves packaging the script and readying it for use on the computing platform. It's necessary whenever changes are made to the script's interface (inputs/outputs) or its dependencies.
3. Deploy the Software: This final step allows the script to run on the computing platform within the virtual laboratory where it's been uploaded.

Moreover, there's a Repackage function, useful for updating an already published script that has undergone modifications without altering its inputs/outputs or dependencies.

Once imported, scripts become exploitable through the DataMiner component GUI which presents two panels (Figure 5):

Figure 7.1 Blue-Cloud VRE Software and Algorithms Importer Interface

- On the left panel, the GUI presents the list of computational methods available in the VLab, which are semantically categorised (the category is indicated through SAI). For each method, the interface calls the WPS DescribeProcess operation to get the descriptions of the inputs and outputs.
- On the right panel, the GUI presents a form allowing to specify the input parameters of the selected computational method. Input data can be selected from the Workspace clearly.

DM is a Java-based Web Service (built on the 52°North WPS framework) operating on Apache Tomcat, enhanced with gCube libraries. The DM architecture consists of two server clusters within a Virtual VRE: the Master Cluster and the Workers Cluster, as shown in Figure 7.1. Typically, each cluster comprises 16 servers managed by a HA-Proxy load balancer, which evenly distributes requests. Every server runs a DM service, which informs the Resource Registry of its presence and capabilities. The Resource Registry indexes the load balancer, which serves as the primary interface for different DMs. The Workers Cluster is dedicated to cloud computations.

Figure 7.2 Blue-Cloud VRE Execution Space Interface

Figure 7.3 The DataMiner System architecture

The Master and Workers clusters are dynamically set up by D4Science, using an orchestration engine with Ansible scripts for consistent, reliable configuration of multi-tier applications.

Upon receiving a WPS request, the Master Cluster's balancer allocates it to one of its services (master DM). These DMs host various processes from multiple developers, including both local and cloud algorithms. Local algorithms execute directly on the master DMs, making use of parallel processing and significant memory. Cloud algorithms, on the other hand, operate on distributed computing principles like MapReduce and depend on the Workers Cluster's DMs (cloud nodes).

DM enhances the standard 52°North WPS implementation with features that promote user collaboration and result repeatability and reusability. This is achieved through the integration of common services in

the infrastructure. Notably, DataMiner can process inputs from workspace folders shared among users, facilitating collaborative complex experiments. Inputs can also be received via HTTP links or embedded in WPS execution requests. The computation outputs are first stored in distributed cloud storage and then returned to the client. Subsequently, a separate thread makes these results accessible in the user's workspace. After each computation, a workspace folder is created containing inputs, outputs, parameters, and a provenance document summarising this data. This folder, shareable with others, allows for the re-execution and sharing of the entire execution process, thereby encouraging collaborative experimentation.

3.1.3. Analytics Engines Comparison

Table 1 compares the two different systems: Data Miner and CCP, focusing on various features relevant to their functionalities, across various technical aspects.

For virtualisation, Data Miner utilises “classic” virtual machines whereas CCP employs containers with isolated runtime. In terms of execution infrastructures, Data Miner's infrastructure is chosen by VLab management per VLab, while CCP offers multiple infrastructures selectable by users. For standard protocols, Data Miner uses OGC WPS (XML), contrasting with CCP's OGC API Processes (JSON).

The Method integration in Data Miner is handled through the SAI with GitHub support, while CCP integrates via Method Importer and supports any Code Versioning System (CVS). Data Miner excels in parallel executions, including MapReduce, whereas CCP's parallel execution support is basic but expected to improve. Regarding the availability of methods, Data Miner has many ready-to-use options, in contrast to CCP's fewer out-of-the-box methods. Both systems integrate with JupyterLab and RStudio, but CCP's integration is notably easier, also due to a code generation tool. Finally, the front-end technology of Data Miner is based on Rich Internet Applications (RIA), whereas CCP uses a web component-based approach, exportable in multiple Content Management Systems (CMS).

Table 1 Synoptic table comparing the DataMiner and CCP engines features

Features	Data Miner	CCP
Virtualisation	Virtual Machines	Containers, isolated runtime
Execution Infrastructures	Per VLab, selectable by VLab mgmt.	Multiple, selectable by users
Standard protocol	OGC WPS (XML)	OGC API Processes (JSON), OGC WPS (XML)
Method Integrations tool	Software Importer (SAI), Github support	Method Importer / Your IDE, any CVS support
Parallel Executions	Yes, also Map Reduce	Basic, more support will be added

out-of-the-box methods availability	Many	Few
JupyterLab and Rstudio integrations	Yes	Yes, Easier (Code generation tool)
Front-end technology	RIA	Web Component based, exportable in multiple CMS

The comparison between Data Miner and CCP reveals distinct strengths and preferences in their approach to analytics. Data Miner, with its use of classic virtual machines, excels in parallel executions and offers a wide range of ready-to-use methods, making it robust and immediately functional. Its integration through SAI and GitHub support indicates a focus on established technologies although with a learning curve that may be steeper.

On the other hand, CCP's use of containers and a web component-based front-end technology demonstrates a modern, flexible approach, allowing for a customisable user experience and easier integration with popular platforms like JupyterLab and RStudio.

Moreover, CCP's support for multiple infrastructures and a broader range of CVS, along with its potential for improvement in parallel execution capabilities, shows a system designed for adaptability and future growth. While each system has its unique advantages, the choice between Data Miner and CCP would largely depend on the specific needs of the scientific community, whether it be immediate, out-of-the-box functionality or a more customizable, modern approach.

3.2. JupyterHub

JupyterHub is an open-source web application that allows multiple users to access and use Jupyter notebooks within a shared computing environment. It is particularly valuable in educational and research contexts, as it simplifies the deployment and management of Jupyter notebooks for multiple users. Notebooks are increasingly recognised as the standard tool for offering an easy-to-use online coding system coupled with interactive computing. In the Blue-Cloud VRE, the establishment and management of a Notebook service that integrates with the Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs must meet several key criteria:

- The service must be seamlessly integrated and accessible through various Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs;
- It should be harmonised with the Blue-Cloud VRE Identity and Access Management Service (cf. Section 6.1);
- Access to the Blue-Cloud Storage services (cf. Section 5) is essential, enabling users to interact with files in the VLabs directly from the Notebook environment.
- Users should have the option to select from diverse Notebook versions, differing in pre-installed software and hardware specifications.
- There should be a facility for users to publish their notebooks within the Blue-Cloud VRE catalogue (cf. Section 4).

JupyterHub for Blue-Cloud relies on Kubernetes² for the management of the user workloads. This setup provides a robust Notebook service offering uninterrupted access from the graphical interface of the Blue-Cloud VLabs. There are two installations available for the VRE: one relying on the Blue-Cloud VRE Kubernetes cluster available on CNR premises and a second one installed on a dedicated Kubernetes cluster deployed on GKE (Google Kubernetes Engine)³ - Google Cloud's managed service for running containerized applications. In both installations, Kubernetes provides a common abstraction layer that facilitates replication of the service across different hardware setups without changes in configuration, good isolation between users, allows for easy scaling of resources available to users and it provides good flexibility to tune the system to the specific parameters of the hosting environment.

The reference architecture for the JupyterHub solution within the Blue-Cloud VRE is illustrated in Figure 8. The Kubernetes solution automates the provisioning of Notebook servers. These servers, functioning as containers, provide users with options to choose specific image flavours and set limitations on CPU and RAM usage for each instance. The flexibility of the Kubernetes environment allows for scalable deployment, enabling the addition of new machines (worker nodes) to the existing cluster to enhance service capacity as needed.

² <https://kubernetes.io/>

³ <https://docs.cloud.google.com/kubernetes-engine/docs>

Figure 8 Jupyter Hub solution reference architecture

The project Zero to JupyterHub⁴ is pivotal in deploying JupyterHub on Kubernetes. It offers a range of customizable add-ons crucial for integration within the Blue-Cloud framework. For Blue-Cloud installations there are several customisations included in the setup described: the integration with the Blue-Cloud Identity and Access Management Service (cf. section 6.1) and the Information System (cf. Section 6.2); persistent volumes supporting concurrent access by multiple users; and a plugin-based configuration for supporting spawning dedicated user servers to host interactive applications beyond the default JupyterLab.

The extension of JupyterHub’s authentication system to incorporate the Blue-Cloud Identity and Access Management Service is performed through a specialised JupyterHub Authenticator class. This class extends JupyterHub OAuthenticator⁵ to retrieve a user’s personal OpenID Connect token from a VLab and employ it to query the Information System to determine permissions and available server configuration available in the JupyterHub interface.

JupyterHub allows users to run different server instances (which might differ in hardware specifications or pre-installed libraries) according to the user’s needs. As depicted in Figure 9 and 10, within the Blue-Cloud VRE JupyterHub is used to spawn both JupyterLab Notebooks and RStudio applications on the selected dedicated VRE Cloud servers. Independently from the fact that they are JupyterLab Notebooks or RStudio, Blue-Cloud offers different instances and the possibility to customise them based on the VLab requirements. These instances are similar in capacity and have ready-to-use libraries that are useful to conduct the activities of Blue-Cloud V Labs. Images are automatically built and published to a container registry (e.g., DockerHub) to make them available for the Kubernetes cluster. The system is highly flexible,

⁴ <https://zero-to-jupyterhub.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁵ <https://oauthenticator.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

so new servers can be easily allocated as needed in Blue-Cloud, in order to meet the demands and needs of the users. The list of available servers available (including hardware configuration and container images to use) for each user is dynamically obtained from the Information System without the need of reconfiguring or restarting the JupyterHub system.

Figure 9 Blue-Cloud JupyterLab dedicated server for VLab Carbon Plankton Dynamics

Figure 10 Blue-Cloud RStudio dedicated server for VLab Carbon Plankton Dynamics

Additional integration steps were undertaken to enable access to the Blue-Cloud VRE workspace. This access is established using the StorageHub Fuse library, enabling the mounting of user workspace folders within the Notebook environment. This feature is enabled by the **StorageHub Fuse** component, a custom component developed to work with the Linux Filesystem in Userspace (FUSE)⁶ software interface. This connects the Linux filesystem and the Blue-Cloud VRE workspace backend service, i.e., the StorageHub service (cf. section 5.1). The library integration ensures that the workspace can be mounted in a sidecar

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Filesystem_in_Userspace

container (a specific container that runs with the main container to provide extra functionality) alongside the user's primary Notebook container, and it is accessible within the user's home directory.

Furthermore, the Kubernetes cluster was configured with an NFS server to accommodate persistent user volumes. This configuration allows for provided working directories for users and supporting shared Dataspace (c.f. Section 5.2) for each VLab that can be accessed concurrently and safely by multiple users. In the case of the Blue-Cloud VRE Kubernetes cluster, a dedicated NFS server is run in one of the cluster nodes with extra storage capacity. For the GKE setup, the system relies on Google's FileStore⁷ solution, which delivers a managed NFS service for shared file storage. Thanks to the usage of Kubernetes Persistent Volumes that abstract the underlying physical storage details, the JupyterHub does not require any changes in configuration.

Expanding the Blue-Cloud VRE to support high-performance computing required addressing several infrastructure constraints within the Google Cloud Platform (GCP). The main objective was to enable GPU acceleration in support of advanced AI and simulation workflows within Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs. To this end, a dedicated configuration of Google Kubernetes Engine (GKE) was designed to accommodate the limited availability and strict zoning requirements of high-end GPU hardware, including NVIDIA H100 and T4 devices. The solution is based on dynamically managed node pools capable of provisioning GPU-enabled worker nodes across multiple availability zones. By adopting an infrastructure-as-Code approach, the system ensures reliable and repeatable deployment of GPU resources despite the inherent volatility of public cloud availability, thereby enabling scalable access to high-performance compute capacity (see the [GKE cluster configuration repository](#)).

At the application level, additional effort was required to ensure full compatibility between containerised Notebook environments and the underlying GPU hardware. The team developed and automated the build of specialised Docker images that align machine-learning frameworks with specific hardware and CUDA requirements (e.g. CUDA compute capability 7.0). This work resulted in the implementation of CI/CD pipelines that produce GPU-ready Notebook images for PyTorch and Julia, using compliant Terraform and Ansible configurations (see the [PyTorch Notebook GPU repository](#) and [notebooks-operations repository](#)). To ensure controlled and cost-effective use of GPU resources, the JupyterHub Spawner component was also enhanced. The spawning logic was refactored to enforce fine-grained role-based access control, exposing GPU-enabled Notebook options only to authorised users and selected Virtual Labs. This approach ensures effective governance of high-cost resources while preserving flexibility for advanced computational use cases (see the [d4science-hub repository](#)).

3.2.1. JupyterLab

JupyterLab represents the latest web-based interactive development environment catering to notebooks, code, and data. Its adaptable interface empowers users to customise and organise their workflows in fields such as data science, scientific computing, and machine learning. JupyterLab is seamlessly

⁷ <https://cloud.google.com/filestore>

integrated, ensuring its smooth operation and management within a clustered environment running within the above described JupyterHub service on Kubernetes as depicted in Figure 8.

Since JupyterHub uses ephemeral storage, all the content stored in that host may be removed at the end of the session. All the data, scripts and other resources that the user needs to persist have to be stored into the Workspace or Dataspace (c.f. Section 5) that are accessible through JupyterLab as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 A Notebook in JupyterLab with access to the external volumes Workspace and Dataspace

3.2.2. RStudio

RStudio enables the execution of real-time statistical analyses using R, a programming language designed for statistical computing and graphics. RStudio is seamlessly integrated, ensuring its smooth operation and management within a clustered environment running within the above-described JupyterHub service on Kubernetes, as depicted in Figure 8.

All the data, scripts, and other resources that the user needs to persist have to be stored in the Workspace or Dataspace (c.f. Section 5) that are accessible through RStudio as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 RStudio instance with access to the external volumes

3.2.3. Other interactive applications

JupyterLab provides support for running additional web-based interactive applications through the Jupyter Server Proxy⁸ extension. This extension lets you run arbitrary external processes alongside the JupyterLab notebook and provide authenticated web access to them.

In the case of the Blue-Cloud VRE, the JupyterHub spawner is extended to run applications on sidecar containers, isolating them from the JupyterLab setup and allowing the application to customise its runtime without any specific restrictions from Jupyter, the only requirement being that the sidecar container serves the application through HTTP or WebSockets. From the JupyterHub side we add a small configuration that will enable the Jupyter Server Proxy extension to forward the application port towards

⁸ <https://jupyter-server-proxy.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

the user and add a check that ensures that the application is already listening to incoming requests before showing the interface to the user to avoid potential race conditions.

An additional sidecar mounting the StorageHub through Fuse and the usage of the persistent volumes through NFS allows applications access the user data without any modification, only agreeing on the path that the volumes should be visible to the application container.

This method is used to support the spawning of user dedicated servers for webODV⁹ and WITOIL (Where is the OIL?)¹⁰, shown in Figure 13 and 14 respectively.

Figure 13 webODV running within the JupyterHub in the Blue-Cloud VRE

⁹ <https://webodv.awi.de/>

¹⁰ <https://witoil.com/>

Figure 14 WITOIL running within the JupyterHub in the Blue-Cloud VRE

3.3. ShinyProxy and Containerised Apps

ShinyProxy offers a robust platform for deploying Shiny applications in enterprise environments, eliminating limitations on concurrent app usage. Shiny, a comprehensive R package, simplifies the creation of interactive web applications directly from R, lately Shiny for Python¹¹ language was also added. These applications can be seamlessly integrated into R Markdown documents or utilised to construct dynamic dashboards, merging R's computational capabilities with the web's interactivity.

Employing ShinyProxy for deploying a Shiny app involves encapsulating the application within an R package, followed by its integration into a Docker image. This methodology brings several significant benefits:

- Isolation and Security: Each user session is managed within a completely isolated environment, bolstering security and stability;
- Flexible Environment Management: Supports various Docker images, accommodating different R and Shiny versions;
- Resource Optimization: Memory and CPU usage can be finely tuned via the Docker API.
- Streamlined Monitoring and Debugging: utilises standard Docker tools for effective system monitoring and troubleshooting.

Blue-Cloud VRE and Containers Orchestration

¹¹ <https://shiny.posit.co/py/>

In the Blue-Cloud VRE, container orchestration is a critical component, utilising both Docker Swarm and Kubernetes:

- Docker Swarm: Manages multiple Docker containers across a virtual machine cluster. Key components include a manager container orchestrating the environment and agent containers ('docker machines') that execute Docker containers. The manager employs a least-utilised algorithm for efficient container allocation.
- Kubernetes: As an additional orchestration tool, Kubernetes offers enhanced scalability and management features. It provides robust mechanisms for automated deployment, scaling, and operation of application containers across clusters of hosts, further augmenting the capabilities of Docker Swarm within the Blue-Cloud VRE.

Overall, these technologies, while catering to ShinyProxy, also effectively support the deployment of other Docker-containerised applications, showcasing their adaptability and scalability in the Blue-Cloud VRE platform.

Figure 15 provides a detailed depiction of a Docker Swarm instance actively managing multiple Docker containers distributed across a cluster of virtual machines. This setup is crucial for ensuring efficient resource allocation and high availability in distributed computing environments. Docker Swarm employs a sophisticated management system, central to which is the manager container. This manager container operates on a designated virtual machine, tasked with the comprehensive management of the Docker environment. It is responsible for deploying containers across various agents within the cluster and continuously monitoring and reporting the status and deployment details of each container, thereby maintaining a cohesive and well-organised cluster.

Figure 15 Blue-Cloud VRE cluster supporting Shiny and any other Docker app

The manager container is not merely a supervisory entity, it represents the primary interface for Docker operations, orchestrating the entire container lifecycle within the Swarm. Agents, functioning as 'docker machines', are critical components of this architecture. These agents, hosted on individual virtual machines, register themselves with the manager and are responsible for running the Docker containers. This registration is pivotal for the distributed nature of Docker Swarm, enabling a seamless, coordinated operation across the cluster.

When a client initiates a request to start a container, the manager's role becomes even more significant. It employs a sophisticated algorithm to locate an appropriate agent with available capacity. This algorithm, known as the least-utilised algorithm, ensures equitable distribution of workload by selecting the agent currently running the fewest number of containers to execute the newly requested container. This strategy not only optimises resource utilisation, rather it also improves the overall efficiency of the system.

Additionally, Docker Swarm's architecture requires additional capabilities for robust operation, especially in complex network environments. These include routing external traffic into the cluster, effectively load balancing across multiple container replicas, and facilitating DNS service discovery. These functionalities are vital for ensuring that Docker containers are accessible and operate efficiently under varying load conditions. To address these needs, the Blue-Cloud VRE integrates the HAProxy load balancer. HAProxy is renowned for its high performance and reliability, making it an ideal choice for managing traffic flow,

ensuring even distribution of requests across the containers, and providing essential DNS resolution services within the Docker Swarm cluster.

3.4. Galaxy

Galaxy¹² is a scientific workflow platform that makes computational workflows accessible to research scientists that do not have computer programming or systems administration experience. Although initially developed for genomics research, it is now largely domain-agnostic and is used as a general workflow management system. Galaxy is a complex Python application with a web-based user interface. With a drag-and-drop interface, users can execute single tools or a set of tools in a workflow directly from the browser. Galaxy hides the complexity from the user and spawns the tools with the right input and makes the output available back in the platform. Galaxy can utilise a wide variety of backends for executing those tools, ranging from dedicated HPC systems to a distributed network of processing endpoints, supporting various managers, including SLURM, Docker, and Kubernetes.

Galaxy for Blue-Cloud VRE is hosted on the dedicated GKE Kubernetes cluster, shared with JupyterHub. Galaxy authentication has been extended to support Blue-Cloud Identity and Access Management Service (cf. section 6.1) so VRE users are properly recognised and authorised within the system. As Galaxy authorisation features are limited and do not allow the customisation of tools for individual users or groups of users, we have deployed a dedicated instance of Galaxy for each VLab requiring access to the tool. While there are multiple instances of the Galaxy frontend, the execution of the workflows shares the same resources of the Kubernetes cluster; thus, the overhead is limited to the web front-end of the platform. The setup relies on NFS for accessing data files across the various instances. Figure 16.1 shows the overall architecture of this setup, while Figure 16.2 shows an actual instance of the running service in the VRE.

¹² <https://galaxyproject.org/>

Figure 16.1 Blue-Cloud VRE Galaxy setup

Figure 16.2 Galaxy service instance in Blue-Cloud VRE

4. Catalogue Framework

The Catalogue Framework is a system realising a flexible and extensible catalogue that has been developed using the open-source data catalogue technology CKAN (ckan.org). It has been enhanced to (a) integrate seamlessly with D4Science services and (b) accommodate a diverse, community-driven, and expandable range of catalogue item types.

Figure 17 depicts the reference architecture of such a framework where (a) the *Catalogue Service* is responsible for the storage and indexing of the metadata of the items published and for supporting the search and browse operation on the catalogue content; (b) the *Catalogue Item Types* is responsible for the definition of item types; (c) the *Catalogue RESTful API* (aka gCat¹³) is a RESTful application for systematically interacting with the Catalogue Service by taking into account the Catalogue Item Types; (d) the *Catalogue Portlet* component implements the main GUI of the entire framework and allows to browse through the catalogue contents; and, (e) the *Publishing Widget* realising a wizard-like GUI component guiding the users to publish items in accordance with the defined item types. Concerning the payloads of

¹³ gCat documentation <https://api.d4science.org/catalogue/docs/index.html>

the catalogue items, these are either referred by URLs or stored in the Storage Framework, in particular in a specific area of the Workspace (cf. Sec. 5).

Figure 17 Blue-Cloud VRE Catalogue solution reference architecture

Figure 18 depicts the data model supported by the Catalogue Framework. In particular, it highlights that, every catalogue item:

- is characterised by **common metadata** (independently of the typology of the item) including (i) a unique identifier, (ii) a title, (iii) a description, (iv) a number of tags, (v) a licence, (vi) a visibility flag (to indicate whether the item is public, i.e. visible to everyone, or private, i.e. the item is visible to VRE members only), (vii) an author, (viii) a maintainer, and (ix) a typology. A typology adds additional metadata (see item-specific metadata);
- Is characterised by **item-specific metadata**. Item-specific metadata depends on an **item profile** specifying a number of *field specifications* each characterising a metadata field by defining: (i) its name, (ii) the mandatory flag (whether the field is mandatory or optional), (iii) the type of field values (i.e. String, Text, Boolean, Number, Geometry in GeoJSON, Time, Time interval, List of Times), (iv) the maximum number of occurrences (i.e. whether the field is repeatable or not), (v) any default value to be proposed, (vi) any accompanying note to facilitate the data entry, (vii) any controlled vocabulary to facilitate the selection of suitable values, (viii) any validator to check the inserted value correctness; Is referring to zero or more **resources**, i.e., objects representing identifiable payloads. Every resource has (i) an Identifier, (ii) the URL where the payload is stored, (iii) a name, (iv) a description, and (v) a format (e.g., CSV, XML).

Figure 18 Blue-Cloud VRE Catalogue framework data mode

Figure 19 reports an (eXtensible Markup Language (XML) snippet of an item profile with a metadata field. In practice, an item profile is an XML document containing the name assigned to the specific typology and a list of metadata field specifications that, besides characterising the information previously described for item-specific metadata, may also contain two directives concerning tagging and group management. The tagging directive instructs the framework to also generate a tag in the common metadata depending on the specific value assigned to the field. The group management directive instructs the framework to assign the catalogue item to a group depending on the value assigned to the specific field.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<metadataformat type="YOUR TYPE HERE">
  <metadatafield categoryref="category_id_#">
    <fieldId>ID of Metadata Field that identifies the field name in the Document (stored in the Service)</fieldId>
    <fieldName>Name of Metadata Field</fieldName>
    <mandatory>true|false</mandatory>
    <dataType>String|Time|Time_Interval|Times_ListOf|Text|Boolean|Number|GeoJSON</dataType>
    <maxOccurs>N|*</maxOccurs>
    <defaultValue>default value</defaultValue>
    <note>[the note is shown as a suggestion in the insert/update metadata form of Catalogue Publisher Widget]
    </note>
    <vocabulary isMultiSelection="true|false">
      <vocabularyField>field1</vocabularyField>
      <vocabularyField>field2</vocabularyField>
      <vocabularyField>field3</vocabularyField>
    </vocabulary>
    <validator>
      <regularExpression>a regular expression for validating values</regularExpression>
    </validator>
    <tagging create="true|false" separator="char_to_separate">onFieldName|onValue|onFieldName_onValue|onValue_onFieldName</tagging>
    <grouping create="true|false">onFieldName|onValue|onFieldName_onValue|onValue_onFieldName</grouping>
  </metadatafield>
</metadataformat>
```

Figure 19 Blue-Cloud VRE Catalogue framework: Metadata field XML Snippet

Concerning gCat, it offers CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operation for the following collections:

- Item Collection, i.e., the set of items managed by the catalogue;
- Resource Collection, i.e., the set of resources of a catalogue item;
- Profile Collection, i.e., the set of profiles characterising the catalogue;
- Namespace Collection, i.e., the set of defined namespaces¹⁴;
- License Collection, i.e., the set of licences that can be associated to a catalogue item;
- Trash Collection, i.e., the set of items deleted that have not been removed yet;

In addition to that, administrators of the catalogue can operate on the following collections: Group Collection; Organization Collection; User Collection; Configuration Collection.

Figure 20 depicts two screenshots of the catalogue portlet. This portlet allows its users to browse through the catalogue contents, search for specific items, and access every catalogue item of interest with its related resources. Moreover, the portlet offers a user-friendly interface for allowing authorised users to manage contents, namely creating new items (via the Publishing Widget), altering existing items and removing items.

¹⁴ A namespace is exploited to augment the semantic of a given field, fields sharing the same namespace are managed as a group of connected fields.

Figure 20 Blue-Cloud VRE Catalogue Web UI for Research Products Catalogue

During the reporting period, Blue Cloud was selected as one of the thirteen candidate EOSC Nodes invited to contribute to the first wave deployment of the EOSC Federation. As shown in Figure 21, this resulted in a dedicated effort to support the onboarding of the Blue Cloud Catalogue into the EOSC Federation. This process resulted in the creation of an additional catalogue instance, as illustrated in Figure 21.

Figure 21 Blue-Cloud VRE Catalogue Web UI for Service Catalogue

This second release of the Catalogue framework introduced a consolidated and more mature version, strengthening its role as the central access point for describing, discovering, and interlinking Blue-Cloud datasets, products, and resources. This release refines the underlying data-model definition and harmonises the representation of heterogeneous scientific assets through an updated set of catalogue profiles and controlled vocabularies, thereby improving semantic consistency across Virtual Laboratories and community-specific collections. Enhancements to the search and discovery layer ensure more accurate retrieval and better ranking of catalogue records, supporting both human-driven exploration and machine-actionable workflows.

Interoperability has been further reinforced through improved alignment with the Storage Framework and the VRE Information System, enabling more coherent integration of catalogue records with associated payloads, provenance information, and computational artefacts. The release also updates the CKAN-based core of the service, integrating the most recent stable components and extensions required to support FAIR-oriented metadata exposure, persistent identifiers, and advanced API-based access patterns.

Overall, this new version of the Catalogue Framework enhances the expressiveness, findability, and interoperability of metadata across Blue-Cloud 2026, while maintaining full continuity with the architecture and mechanisms introduced in the first release. It modernises the service without altering its foundational design, ensuring a stable yet extensible catalogue environment capable of supporting the evolving needs of multidisciplinary marine research communities.

5. Storage Framework

The Storage Framework is composed of several storage technologies operated to deliver two key services: the Workspace and the Dataspace. Both of them work like a typical file system with folders that contain files and other digital items (e.g. hard and soft links), and both of them exploit tailored storage devices. Despite the similarities, the Workspace and the Dataspace are designed to have different features and deliver distinct capabilities, which are synthetically reported in the following sections.

5.1. Workspace

The Workspace provides large, secure and reliable access to a storage volume that contains different spaces:

- VRE space: a shared storage area that is linked to any VLab and accessible by all VLab members;
- Shared space: a storage area that is created by a user and shared with other users;
- Private space: a storage area that is exclusive to any user. It hosts the DataMiner space, where the provenance information of each job run by the DataMiner engine is automatically stored; the VRE Data pool, where the datasets accessed through the Data Discovery & Access service are persisted; the CCP space, where the provenance information of each job run by the Cloud Computing Platform engine is stored upon request of the user.
- Volatile space: a temporary and fast space, where to store transient files that are automatically removed after a configurable period of time, set to one week for the Blue-Cloud community.

Access to shared areas is regulated by selecting one of the following access policies:

- Write Own: users can only update/delete their own files;
- Write Any: any user can update/delete any file;

- Read Only: users can read any file but cannot update/delete.

Regardless of the access policies that control the access of all other users, the VLab Manager has the authority to administer the VRE space that is linked to the VLab under their management and the owner of a shared folder can administer the folder that they choose to share.

Figure 22 depicts the Workspace solution reference architecture. From the top, the workspace service acts as the interface layer, comprising the Workspace Portlet, Widget, and RESTful API. These components serve as the user's entry point to the VRE, facilitating interaction through Web Graphical User Interfaces and programmatic access via an API. The Storage Hub serves as an intermediary abstracting the complexity of data storage and retrieval operations. This layer ensures a seamless integration of the data persistence mechanisms, which are represented at the bottom tier of the architecture. The data persistence layer is indeed split into two distinct storage systems: S3 Storage for data, persisted in an object storage for scalable and secure data storage solutions; and Graph DB for metadata, enabling efficient metadata storage, querying, and management.

Each workspace element, whether a folder or a file, is equipped with metadata, including a name, a description, creation and update dates, the history of actions performed by any user on that element, and the list of versions for the same file. This set of metadata can be easily extended using the APIs of the Workspace service. Additionally, every file may support a content preview automatically generated according to its content type, and it is also possible to make links (as URIs) to it. For folders, these links can enable others to access the folder in "guest mode", without needing to log in. The contextual menu offers shortcuts for some actions on it, such as publishing the item into the catalogue, or initialising a data miner process with the item as input.

Figure 22 Blue-Cloud VRE Workspace solution reference architecture

The workspace supports encryption, compression, replication, versioning, and persistent unique identifiers in an efficient way as follows:

- **Encryption:** it uses a strong encryption algorithm to protect the data from unauthorised access. The encryption keys are managed by D4Science, and depending on the level of control and security required, they may change for each VRE or community. Encryption is applied to data when it is persisted in the cloud and automatically decrypted when accessed via the Workspace interface or APIs;
- **Compression:** it reduces the size of the data by applying a compression algorithm, such as gzip, to save storage space and bandwidth. Compression is performed by D4Science on data when it is persisted in the cloud and automatically decompressed when accessed via the Workspace interface or APIs;
- **Replication:** it ensures the availability and durability of data by replicating it across multiple servers and locations. The replication can be synchronous or asynchronous, depending on the consistency and latency requirements. For the Blue-Cloud VRE, synchronous replication has been selected. With synchronous replication, data is written to both primary and secondary storage devices simultaneously. This ensures that the data is always consistent and up-to-date on all sides. However, this also demands more network capacity and performance and can create latency and complexity. It has been selected to offer the application’s high availability and fast failover. Replication also enables disaster recovery and backup scenarios.
- **Versioning:** it stores multiple versions of a file in the same storage location. This feature lets the user save, access, and restore any version of a file that is stored in the service. With versioning, any user can undo accidental deletion or modification of the data. For example, if the user deletes a file, the Workspace does not erase it completely but moves it to the recycle bin, where it can be

easily restored. If the user overwrites a file, the Workspace creates a new version and retains the old one, assigning a persistent, unique identifier to each version. Each version can be either accessed via the persistent unique identifier or restored as the default version. Versioning enables high availability, durability, and consistency for the data. However, it also consumes more storage space and network bandwidth, as each version of an object is a full copy, not just the differences from the previous version.

- **Persistent Unique Identifier:** it assigns a unique, web-friendly, and persistent identifier to any file and folder stored by it. This identifier does not depend on the location or content of the object, but rather on the metadata written in the Workspace. It can be used to access the object using two types of persistent URLs (PURL) associated with it by the Workspace. The first type of PURL is a link to either the file or the folder that validates the access policies associated with it by verifying the user's identity and access privileges. The second type of PURL is a link to either the file or the folder that enables anonymous access to it.

The Volatile space is configured to lack replication and versioning, delivering low latency and faster read and write speeds. Persistent unique identifiers, such as UUIDs, are used to access files via the Workspace APIs.

5.2. Dataspace

The Dataspace provides large and secure access to a storage volume, allowing users to access and share files over a network, as if they were stored locally. It can be configured with different access control lists (ACL) to enable either read-only mode or read-write mode according to the user role in the VRE.

Unlike the workspace, the Dataspace is designed to be stateless. This means that the Dataspace does not store any information about the user's activities, and therefore, the history of operations performed on the file is not supported. This enables efficient and fast recovery from crashes.

The Dataspace lacks features such as encryption, compression, replication, versioning and persistent unique identifiers. However, it compensates for these limitations by providing large volumes (in the order of TBs) with significantly faster read and write speed, lower latency, and lower congestion compared to the Workspace.

Figure 23 Blue-Cloud VRE Dataspace solution reference architecture

Figure 24 highlights the main pros and cons of the Workspace and Dataspace services.

Figure 24 Blue-Cloud VRE Workspace vs. Dataspace; Persistent vs. Volatile storage

The second release of the Storage Framework featured a significant architectural evolution, with the migration of the underlying S3-based storage system to a Ceph Object Storage solution. CEPH provides an S3-compatible interface while enabling a fully distributed and highly resilient storage backend based on a combination of object storage, replication services, and automated self-healing. This architectural change strengthens the reliability and scalability of the Storage Framework by removing single points of failure and improving consistency guarantees for data-intensive scientific workloads.

The migration to CEPH introduced improvements in storage durability due to native data replication across multiple nodes, as well as more predictable performance under concurrent access. The transition has been carried out without altering the logical design of the Workspace and Dataspace services, which

continue to operate through their standard APIs while benefitting from the enhanced robustness of the new backend.

In addition to this major evolution, regular maintenance and optimisation activities were performed across the Storage Framework services. Several issues related to version history management, persistent URL generation, and the propagation of access policies across shared areas were resolved to ensure consistent behaviour during intensive usage. Performance optimisations were also applied within the Storage Hub layer, with particular attention to metadata serialisation in the GraphDB backend and the mitigation of latency peaks during replication or synchronisation events.

Further improvements were introduced to increase the robustness of the Volatile space through strengthened cleanup routines and enhanced monitoring, preventing residual temporary artefacts from impacting storage quotas and user operations. Incremental refinements were also applied to the Workspace REST API to enhance the clarity of error reporting and support more resilient handling of long-running operations.

From an operational perspective, alignment with the security practices recommended for CEPH-based S3 deployments was ensured throughout the period, including regular reviews of encryption key procedures and authentication workflows. These activities guarantee continued compliance with the security requirements expected from a data-intensive scientific infrastructure.

Overall, the introduction of the CEPH-based storage backend together with the continuous optimisation of the Workspace and Dataspace services provides a more reliable, secure, and predictable Storage Framework. The architecture remains consistent with the Blue Cloud design principles while offering improved scalability and resilience to support the growing needs of the Blue Cloud community.

6. Enabling Framework

6.1. Identity and Access Management

The IAM (Identity and Access Management) system, developed during the previous Blue-Cloud Project, features a specialised IAM Service that oversees User Identity and Authorisation, including the login process. Keycloak¹⁵, a component recognised for its industry-standard quality in IAM software, efficiently manages all aspects of Identity Management workflows. This encompasses seamless integration with various Identity Providers such as Google, LinkedIn, and the EOSC Portal.

As shown in Figure 25, the VRE Gateway service, utilising Liferay web portal technology, is designed to store only the essential user information necessary for its navigational and visualisation functions. It

¹⁵ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

operates on a user information cache that is updated with each user login, thereby minimising its dependence on specific technologies, versions, and bespoke code artefacts.

A key component of the updated IAM architecture is the Orchestrator service, which facilitates the creation of workflows that an engine subsequently executes. The primary objective of these orchestrator workflows is to reduce the load on services acting as event sources. These services are no longer required to orchestrate or be aware of complex details independently. User-related events originating from these services, including the IAM, are dispatched to the Orchestrator. The Orchestrator then assumes the responsibility of informing the relevant services directly by implementing the necessary workflow. Finally, the IAM service transfers data to a LDAP server (based on 389DS) within the Blue-Cloud VRE. This server is utilised by several key tools: (a) the software code repository tool (Gitea-based), (b) the software integration tool (Jenkins-based), and (c) the issue tracker tool (Redmine-based). These tools employ the server for authenticating project members, enabling them to access these resources using their Blue-Cloud credentials. This IAM solution is notable for its interoperability, adhering to open standards like OAuth2, User-Managed Access (UMA), and OpenID Connect (OIDC) protocols. The incorporation of UMA and OIDC, building upon the OAuth2¹⁶ protocol, represents a significant enhancement. UMA focuses primarily on Authorisation, providing a streamlined protocol for centralised access control. It enables resource owners to establish detailed authorisation policies on a centralised server, which then controls access to these resources. OpenID Connect (OIDC) adds an identity layer to OAuth2, utilising JSON Web Tokens (JWT). This enables third-party applications to verify the user's identity through an Authorisation Server and to access basic user profile information. The effectiveness and efficiency of OIDC in identity verification, as evidenced during the Blue-Cloud Project, have been well-demonstrated and highly valued in various applications.

Figure 25 IAM Solution Reference Architecture

The second release of the IAM services introduced a set of developments connected to the integration with the EOsc Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure. These activities were driven by the

¹⁶ <https://oauth.net/2/>

selection of Blue-Cloud as one of the thirteen candidate EOSC Nodes and by its invitation to contribute to the first wave deployment of the EOSC Federation. As a result, a significant part of the work focused on enabling full support for the EOSC AAI Federation. Within this framework, each EOSC Node is required to operate at least one Infrastructure Proxy. This component is responsible for brokering authentication events and routing requests to the services offered by the Node. Nodes participating in the federation must rely on the Identity Layer provided by the EOSC AAI Federation and must establish a connection to the Hub, known as MyAccessID, which performs cross node token validation. Each Infrastructure Proxy is registered as a single relying party, representing the EOSC Node within the federation. All relying parties participating in this ecosystem must adopt standard OpenID Connect or OAuth2 protocols to support their authentication and authorisation flows. This ensures consistent interaction across federated services and enables secure and interoperable access to the Blue-Cloud VRE and its associated services.

To support identity federation across EOSC Nodes, the EOSC Node Federation mandates that each Node extends its standard access-token validation logic. In addition to performing local token introspection, a Node must also be capable of validating tokens issued by other EOSC Nodes. This cross-node validation is delegated to MyAccess, which acts as the federation-level authority for token verification. MyAccess also supports tokens issued by the central D4Science IAM Keycloak, used extensively by Blue-Cloud services including the website, Gateway, VREs, Virtual Labs, and Jupyter instances, thus introspection requests for these tokens are also accepted within the federation. Initially, this validation model relied on enhancing the standard OAuth2 introspection flow through a dedicated middleware component, the Token Introspection Proxy (TIP). TIP extends the basic introspection endpoint to satisfy the EOSC Federation's requirements. However, its deployment required network-level adjustments (DNS, routing, proxy interception) to redirect calls that would normally reach the native Keycloak introspection endpoint.

To support a seamless integration within the EOSC Federation, an additional approach was developed by extending the Keycloak introspection endpoint itself. The resulting module performs all cross-node checks, token transformations, and claim enrichments required by the federation. As illustrated in Figure 24, the introduction of the TIP component adds a federated introspection layer to the IAM architecture. TIP is deployed alongside Keycloak and acts as the entry point for all access-token validation requests. A dedicated routing/proxy layer is configured to transparently intercept calls to the native Keycloak introspection endpoint and redirect them to TIP. TIP then manages both local and cross-node validation by forwarding local introspection requests to Keycloak and delegating external-token validation to the EOSC Hub (MyAccessID). All other components in the architecture remain unchanged and seamlessly benefit from the enhanced federated token-validation workflow.

The Keycloak extension relies on a configuration file that defines how to handle introspection requests for tokens issued by external EOSC Nodes and used within the Blue-Cloud ecosystem. The same configuration also specifies optional token-claim mappings, allowing transformations of claim values returned by external nodes so that they match internal domain conventions. This reproduces the claim-translation behaviour previously implemented in TIP. Importantly, the module uses the same configuration format as TIP, ensuring full compatibility and simplifying configuration management, particularly when the file is maintained or distributed directly by EOSC.

Besides the work related to the EOSC AAI activities, the second release comprised a system upgrade, through a Major Version update of the Keycloak open source IAM software. Specifically, from Keycloak version 19 to version 24. This migration not only ensured alignment with the latest software lifecycle, but also introduced significant improvements in security, interoperability, configurability, and user experience, thereby strengthening the overall IAM architecture of Blue-Cloud. In particular, Keycloak 24 delivered several enhancements:

- User Profile and Progressive Profiling have become fully supported and enabled by default. Administrators can now configure user attributes with far greater granularity, while the login, registration, and account-management pages dynamically adapt to realm-specific configurations.
- Improvements to the JavaScript client include the use of the exports field in package.json, offering better compatibility with modern bundlers (e.g., Vite, Webpack 5). In addition, PKCE (S256) is now enabled by default for OIDC authorisation flows, increasing the security of browser-based applications.
- Various performance, stability, and scalability enhancements have also been incorporated. These include improved brute-force protection, preventing concurrent authentication attempts to mitigate attacks and optimised handling of user consent removal when client scopes or realms are deleted.
- Additional flexibility has been added for enterprise-level configurations, such as enhanced LDAP connection-pool options and improved truststore handling. These are particularly relevant in Blue-Cloud, where Keycloak integrates with a 389DS LDAP backend used by Gitea, Jenkins, and Redmine for unified authentication.

Collectively, these updates provide a more secure, resilient, and future-proof IAM environment for the Blue-Cloud VRE. The upgrade to Keycloak version 24, carried out between M13 and M36, represents a strategic investment in the long-term maintainability, standards compliance, and operational robustness of the platform.

6.2. Information System

The purpose of the Information System (IS) is to provide access to well-organised information. In the Blue-Cloud VRE, such information is related to the set of resources (data, services, and tools) describing the VRE. The Blue-Cloud VRE manages a combination of these resources, offering capabilities and capacities for data-driven research via the Virtual Laboratories (VLabs).

To effectively monitor the allocation of these (federated) resources to VLabs, the VRE relies on the IS, which provides capabilities for publishing, discovering, and accessing these resources. Some of these resources are VRE core resources, while others are leveraged from external systems. Hence, the IS has to deal with:

- different set of managed resources: each system composing the federation defines the resources it wishes to contribute to the VRE;

- different models for describing resource characteristics: each system has its own model to define a resource. This mainly means that the same resource type may be described differently by the different organisations contributing to the VRE;
- different workflows governing registration and update of resources: each system may update any resource description at different time-frames and according to different policies.

In the VRE, the subset of resources exposed to a VLab are usually different from the subset exposed to another VLab. The subset of resources of a VLab can intersect (and usually does) the subset of resources of another VLab. A change that occurs to one or more resources exposed to different VLabs must be reflected consistently across all VLabs.

In the IS, the resources are defined using a model known as the IS Model, designed at ISTI - CNR [6] to support infrastructure federations such as Blue-Cloud VRE properly. The IS Model employs a graph model framework, which is advantageous in scenarios where the interconnectivity and topological information of data are as significant as the data itself.

Graph models are particularly apt in areas that require detailed mapping of data relationships and structures. In the IS Model, this approach facilitates a dynamic and intricate description of resources through the assembly of various components, or 'bricks', known as 'Facets'. These facets enable a flexible and customisable method for defining resources, meeting the unique requirements of the e-infrastructure.

Figure 25 depicts the IS and VRE Management Systems architecture, central to which is the Resource Registry. This registry plays a central function in the system. Firstly, it empowers the VRE Management System (as detailed in Section 6.3) to establish the necessary context or 'room' for the integration and management of VLab resources. This setting of context is essential for resource incorporation within the Vlab. Secondly, the VRE Management System utilises the registry to define the specific VRE Model – the Blue-Cloud Model. This involves identifying the resources and their facets and mapping the relationships between these resources, ensuring a cohesive and interconnected framework within the VRE. Lastly, the Resource Registry facilitates any Blue-Cloud service to efficiently register, discover, and access resource definitions within the Vlab's operational context. This feature is crucial for the seamless integration and operation of services within the Blue-Cloud ecosystem.

Figure 26 Information System and VRE Management System Reference Architecture

The IS Model is a cornerstone of the Blue-Cloud VRE, offering a sophisticated and adaptable approach to resource management and integration, crucial for the effective functioning of the VRE environment at large.

6.3. VRE Management System

The VRE Management System encompasses a range of services and applications that provide functionalities for the design, creation, and deployment of V Labs. These services facilitate VLab Designers and VRE Managers in using graphical user interfaces to communicate the required features of a desired VLab to the Blue-Cloud infrastructure. They also allow for easy updates to the VLab once it is defined and operational.

Managing these collaborative environments involves a four-stage process:

1. A definition stage where a VLab Designer outlines the features of a new VLab to support a specific application scenario;
2. An approval stage where the VRE Manager decides on the feasibility of the proposed V Labs, determining whether they should be accepted or rejected. For accepted V Labs, the VRE Manager also decides on deployment details, such as the hosting nodes to be used;
3. A verification stage where the VRE Manager validates the VLab as per the specifications approved earlier;
4. A management stage where the VRE Manager customises certain elements of a deployed VLab (such as the layout of the user interface components, known as portlets) and monitors the overall operational status of the VRE.

For more comprehensive information, visit the gCube Wiki page dedicated to this service at https://wiki.gcube-system.org/gcube/VRE_Administration.

This system, which pre-dates the Blue-Cloud initiative, has been redesigned over time to align with evolving technologies.

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